

Alkaloids of *Machilus glaucescens* Wight : Machigline, A New Phenolic Oxoaporphine Alkaloid

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Machigline (I), a new phenolic oxoaporphine alkaloid, isolated along with atheroline (II) and β -sitosterol-O- β -D-glucoside from the alcohol extract of the leaves of *Machilus glaucescens* Wight (Lauraceae), has been shown to be 1,2-methylenedioxy-9-hydroxy-10-methoxyoxoaporphine by spectral and chemical studies. A fatty ketol characterised as a rarely occurring *n*-hentriacontan-10-ol-16-one ($\equiv$ 10-hydroxypalmitone) (III) (first report of its occurrence in Lauraceae) has also been isolated as an aliphatic constituent from the CHCl_3 extract of the plant besides the lignan and nor-lignan constituents. The mass fragmentations of I and III have been delineated. The isolation of machigline and atheroline constitutes the first report on the occurrence of oxoaporphines in *Machilus* species, and machigline adds a new name to the list of only a few phenolic oxoaporphines.

THE family Lauraceae is a well-known rich source of alkaloids and some *Machilus* species are reported to elaborate benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline and aporphine alkaloids¹⁻³. Earlier, we reported⁴ the isolation, structure elucidation and synthesis of three new nor-lignans viz., machicendiol, machicenonol and machicenin from *Machilus glaucescens*. We now report the isolation of a new phenolic oxoaporphine alkaloid designated machigline⁵ (I) along with atheroline (II)^{6,7} and β -sitosterol-O- β -D-glucoside from the alcohol extract of the plant material and the isolation of a rarely occurring ketol 10-hydroxypalmitone⁸ (III) from the CHCl_3 extract as the major aliphatic constituent of the plant.

The minor alkaloid machigline crystallising from chloroform-methanol as glistening red needles, m.p. 315° (d), $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ (M^+ 321.0620), $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, has been assigned structure (I) on the basis of spectral and chemical studies. Machigline is insoluble in common non-polar solvents but fairly soluble in alcohol and methanolic-chloroform and forms red solution with mineral acids. The intensity and the variation of colour of machigline in solution

from yellow to pink and to red depend on the concentration and the pH of the medium. This behaviour is reminiscent of phenolic oxoaporphine alkaloids^{6,7}. The presence of the phenolic hydroxyl

group is also suggested by positive FeCl_3 colouration. Its solubility in Na_2CO_3 solution indicates its enhanced acidity compared to simple phenols. The oxygenation sites in the oxoaporphine skeleton as

TABLE I—UV AND VISIBLE ABSORPTIONS OF MACHIGLINE AND Atheroline

Compound	λ_{max} (EtOH)		λ_{max} (EtOH + HCl)		λ_{max} (EtOH + NaOH)	
	nm	log ϵ	nm	log ϵ	nm	log ϵ
Machigline	249	4.23	258	4.19	254	4.28
	272	4.12	281	4.10	304	4.26
	285	4.04	379	3.92	326	4.21
					351	3.79
	351	3.70	509	3.27	382	3.43
	385	3.22				
	430	3.18			537	3.28
Atheroline	244	4.12	257	4.10	252	4.12
	273	4.17	282	4.10	294	3.99
	292 (sh)	3.96	385	4.05	320	3.98
	355	3.90	500	3.38	390	3.74
	380	3.83			535	3.46
	435	3.60				

well as the location of the hydroxyl function was settled from a comparative study of its uv and visible spectra (Table 1) with those of the congener alkaloid atheroline⁶ and other phenolic oxoaporphines⁹. Machigline displays a very characteristic 1,2-methylenedioxy phenolic oxoaporphine uv spectrum. It contains one methoxyl group (pmr and ms) and thus it appears to be a 1,2-methylenedioxy methoxy phenolic oxoaporphine. The close similarity of the uv and visible spectra of machigline and atheroline in different media and similar bathochromic shifts of λ_{max} values in alkali [phenolate anion from machigline is comparable in energy to that from atheroline] indicate the same location (C-9) for OH in both the alkaloids thus allowing delocalisation of the charge of the phenolate anion to nitrogen. Any other alternative position for phenolic OH group would have given rise to different uv maxima in alkali medium due to different mesomeric stabilisation of the phenolate ion⁶. In machigline, like atheroline, the greater mesomeric stabilisation of the phenolate ion accounts for its well-marked acidic properties compared to simple phenols. The ir spectrum (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) of machigline exhibited characteristic bands for OH (3520), conjugated CO (1635) in the highly aromatic oxoaporphine system (1575, 1522) and methylenedioxy¹⁰ (962) group.

The pmr spectra of machigline and atheroline show close similarity in the aromatic region suggesting the same positions of oxygenation functions in them. The pmr spectrum (80 MHz, d_6 -DMSO) of machigline (Table 2) clearly shows a methylenedioxy grouping on the planar oxoaporphine ring system as a two proton singlet^{11,12} at δ 6.48, an aromatic methoxyl at δ 3.96 (3H, s) and the five aromatic protons in δ 7.46-8.71 region and the hydroxyl proton at δ 9.9 (1H, s). The placement of methylenedioxy group is made by a comparative study of the pmr spectra of some methylenedioxy oxoaporphines in conjunction with the uv and mass spectral analysis. The chemical shifts of methylenedioxy and methoxyl protons in oxoaporphines vary with their locations. It is known that a methylenedioxy group located at 1,2 resonates at a lower field (δ 6.5-6.85) than if located at 9,10 (δ 6.2)^{7,13,14}. The presence of an aromatic singlet at δ 7.46 due to H-3 resonating at higher field than other aromatic protons eliminates the possibility of methoxyl group

being at C-3 (moreover a C-3 methoxyl appears between δ 4.43-4.55 i.e., a comparatively lower field⁹). The two one proton doublets centred at δ 8.71 and 7.92 are assignable to H-5 (α to N) and H-4, respectively ($J_{4,5} = J_{5,4} = 5$ Hz) of the pyridine moiety. The appearance of the remaining two aromatic protons as two singlets indicates the adjacent positions of hydroxyl and methoxyl groups at C-9 and C-10 or vice-versa. The singlet at δ 8.03 is due to H-11 which in oxoaporphines appears more downfield⁹ than H-3, H-8, H-9 or H-10 and that at δ 7.66 is assigned to H-8 (adjacent to 9-OH) appearing at the same field in both machigline and atheroline.

SCHEME 1 MASS FRAGMENTATION OF MACHIGLINE

The conversion of machigline to dicentrone^{15,16} (IV) ($\equiv$ 1,2-methylenedioxy-9,10-dimethoxyoxoaporphine) by treatment with excess CH_2N_2 in methanolic solution confirms the skeleton and the oxygenation sites at 1,2,9 and 10 positions. The location of the hydroxyl group at C-9 has been

 TABLE 2—CHEMICAL SHIFT (δ) OF PMR SIGNALS OF MACHIGLINE, ATHEROLINE AND THEIR ACETATES (VARIAN CFT-20, 80 MHz)

Compounds (Solvent)	-O-CH ₂ -O	Aromatic protons					C ₉ -OH	OCH ₃ (1,2)	C ₁₀ -OCH ₃	C ₉ -O-CO-CH ₃
		H-3	H-4	H-5	H-8	H-11				
Machigline (d_6 -DMSO)	6.48	7.46	7.92	8.71	7.66	8.03	9.9	—	3.96	—
Machigline acetate (CDCl ₃)	6.48	7.12	7.65	8.82	7.99	8.16	—	—	3.95	2.02
Atheroline (d_6 -DMSO)	—	7.46	7.91	8.69	7.67	8.56	9.91	3.95, 3.98	3.95	—
Atheroline acetate (CDCl ₃)	—	7.12	7.67	8.81	8.00	8.70	—	3.96, 4.02	4.02	2.2

conclusively settled by observing the 0.33 and 0.13 ppm downfield shifts of H-8 and H-11 respectively (*ortho* and *meta* to acetoxy group) in machigline acetate, m.p. 240° (d) compared to machigline itself which are the same as those in atheroline acetate relative to atheroline. The mass fragmentation¹⁷ (Scheme 1) pattern of machigline is in good agreement with the proposed structure (I). The spectrum shows loss of one methyl from the molecular ion (M^+ 321.0620) peak and the other ion peaks originated through the loss of CH_2O and a number of CO units. Thus, on the basis of the spectral studies in conjunction with the chemical observations, machigline is correctly formulated as (I). Moreover, there is report of natural occurrence of oxoaporphines bearing hydroxyl function at 9- but not at 10-position e.g., atheroline, subsessiline¹⁸ and oxoanobline¹⁹. The known congener alkaloid atheroline was isolated as a major constituent as a dirty yellow solid, $C_{19}H_{12}O_5N$ (M^+ 337), m.p. 248-50° (d) and its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample. It is worthwhile recording the

pmr spectrum of atheroline itself (Table 2) as it has not been reported earlier.

The major aliphatic constituent $C_{31}H_{62}O_2$ (M^+ 466.4660), m.p. 96°, isolated from chloroform extract was characterised as 10-hydroxypalmitone (III) which was first isolated from sandal leaves⁸. This fatty ketol [ir peaks at 1705, 3300 (br) cm^{-1}] afforded an acetate, m.p. 43°. No spectral details of this compound and its $NaBH_4$ reduction product (VII) (which is not naturally or synthetically known) are available in literature and these are also reported in the present paper. The compound (III) showed pmr signals ($CDCl_3$, TMS) at δ 3.6 (1H, m, -CHOH), 2.39 [t, $J=7$ Hz, 4 H, two CH_2 (a and b)], 1.27 [b s, 50 H, (CH_2)₂₈] and 0.89 [t, $J=6$ Hz, 6 H, two CH_3 groups]. The mass spectral analysis (Scheme 2) is quite interesting and is helpful to find the positions of carbonyl and hydroxyl groups. $NaBH_4$ reduction of the ketonic alcohol yielded the straight chain diol, $C_{31}H_{64}O_2$ (M^+ 468), *n*-hentriacontan-10,16-diol (VII) showing pmr signals at

Scheme—2 Mass fragmentation of *n*-hentriacontan-10-ol-16-one

δ 3.55 [2H, *m*, two -CHOH], 1.26 [*b s*, 54 H, (CH₂)_{2,7}] and 0.86 [*t*, J=6 Hz, 6 H, two CH₃]. The absence of any triplet around δ 2.39 for ketomethylenes as in III as well as the absence of any carbonyl band in the ir spectrum of VII confirms the complete conversion of III into the diol (VII). The mass spectrum of the diol (VII) showed ion peaks at *m/e* 450 (M⁺-H₂O), 432 (*m/e* 450-H₂O) indicating the presence of two hydroxyl groups and appearance of a number of other peaks due to subsequent loss of methylenes. The isolation of atheroline and machigline marks the first occurrence of oxoaporphines in a *Machilus* species and machigline adds a new name to the list of only a few natural phenolic oxoaporphines.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in H₂SO₄ bath and are uncorrected. The uv spectra were recorded on a Varion Techtron series 634 spectrophotometer in aldehyde free 95% ethanol. IR spectra were taken in KBr pellets with Beckmann IR-20 or Pye Unicam SP 1025 spectrometer and the optical rotations were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 241 polarimeter in CHCl₃ and ethanol solutions. PMR spectra of the original alkaloids were determined in d₆-DMSO and those of the acetates of the alkaloids and other compounds in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal standard with a Varian CFT-20 spectrometer. Silica gel (60-120 mesh) was used for chromatography of main columns and silica gel (100-200 mesh) for side columns. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was used for drying organic solvents. R_f values were measured over tlc on silica gel G.

Extraction : The marc left after pet. ether and CHCl₃ extraction of the dried and powdered leaves of *Machilus glaucescens* was kept immersed in EtOH (90%) for 20 days. The gummy brown residue (15 g) obtained from the alcohol extract responded to Dragendorff test for alkaloids. A small part of the residue (4 g) was repeatedly extracted with cold 2*N* HCl (4 × 100 ml) till the fresh extract showed negative test for alkaloid. The combined acid extract (400 ml) was cooled, basified with 2*N* NH₄OH solution and extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 150 ml). The combined CHCl₃ extract (450 ml) was washed, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The deep brown gummy residue (residue-A) was found to be completely soluble in aqueous Na₂CO₃ or NaOH solution showing the presence of phenolic base. The original residue was also found to be almost soluble in Na₂CO₃ solution and negligible precipitation occurred on acidification of the alkali solution. The crude base was almost soluble in both acid and alkali. As the crude base was found to be weakly acidic (phenolic base), the direct chromatography of the crude extract was done over silica gel which effected better result without much loss compared to the case of usual acid extraction. Chromatography of the alcohol extract resulted in isolation of an uncharacterised fatty alcohol (250 mg), m.p. 80°, ν_{max} 3490 cm⁻¹, from the pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluates and β -sitosterol (200 mg), m.p. 138° from the benzene

fractions. The brown residue obtained from the CHCl₃-MeOH (95 : 5) eluates showed three spots of which two were very close on tlc [R_f 0.35, 0.5, 0.53, silica gel G, CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10)]. The last two spots were yellow coloured (concave shaped) and turned pinkish yellow after staining with iodine (phenolic). They showed bright pinkish red uv fluorescence. On repeated chromatography, the CHCl₃-MeOH eluates on concentration showed a white amorphous solid to float on the surface of the deep wine red coloured solution. The white solid on repeated crystallisations from CHCl₃-MeOH-CH₃COCH₃ mixture afforded β -sitosterol-O- β -D-glucoside, m.p. 265-70°d, ν_{max} 3420 (br OH), 2940, 1460, 1372, 1155, 1065 and 1020 cm⁻¹, acetate (Py/Ac₂O, 40 hr, r.t.) m.p. 168°, [α]_D -27° (c, 1.77, CHCl₃), ν_{max} 1740 and 1220 cm⁻¹. Hydrolysis of β -sitosterol-O- β -D-glucoside in 10% H₂SO₄ in aqueous MeOH (reflux 1hr) afforded β -sitosterol after usual work-up and the aqueous sugar part was found to contain D-glucose identified by paper chromatography with authentic sample.

Isolation of atheroline : After separation of β -sitosterol-O- β -D-glucoside, the wine red coloured filtrate was concentrated and found to have two yellow coloured spots, R_f 0.50, 0.53 of varying intensity, similar to those of residue-A obtained by acid extraction of the alcohol extract. The mixed brown residue (1.0 g) was then chromatographed over silica gel (100-200 mesh) but as the R_f values of both the components (phenolic alkaloids) were close, separation by chromatography alone was not possible. Repeated careful fractional crystallisations from CHCl₃-MeOH-ether mixture and chromatography of the mother liquors followed by fractional crystallisations ultimately effected their separation. The major snuff coloured alkaloid (25 mg) was subsequently identified to be atheroline (comparison with an authentic sample obtained through the courtesy of Prof. M. P. Cava), m.p. 248-50°d, R_f 0.54 [silica gel G, CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10), ν_{max} 3270, 1635, 1565, 1505, 1450, 1425, 1350, 1270, 1242, 1220, 1138, 1054 and 1000 cm⁻¹; acetate (Py/Ac₂O, 48 hr, r.t.), m.p. 190°d, crystallised from CHCl₃-pet. ether as yellow needles, ν_{max} 1745, 1640, 1585, 1495, 1450, 1340, 1205, 1110 and 1010 cm⁻¹.

Attempted catalytic hydrogenation of atheroline : Atheroline (8 mg) in AcOH was hydrogenated at r.t. for 2 hr using PtO₂ as catalyst (2 moles of H₂ consumed) to a pale yellow solution which turned reddish brown on exposure to air for work-up. The residue after usual work-up and chromatographic purification was found to be identical with atheroline, m.p. 230°d.

Action of NaBH₄ on atheroline : Atheroline (8 mg) in dry MeOH (8 ml) was treated with excess NaBH₄ (40 mg) and kept for 48 hr. After usual work-up, the resulting yellowish brown mass on chromatography afforded atheroline (5 mg), m.p. 240°d.

Isolation of machigline : After removal of atheroline by repeated chromatography and crystallisations, the mother liquors were mixed and

concentrated. The residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina (B.D.H.). The CHCl_3 -MeOH (80 : 20) eluates on evaporation yielded machigline in poor yield (20 mg) crystallising from MeOH as glistening red needles, R_f 0.5 [CHCl_3 -MeOH (90 : 10)], m.p. 315°d , bright pink fluorescence in uv light, ν_{max} 3520, 1635, 1575, 1522, 1465, 1426, 1355, 1280, 1212, 1140, 1092, 1055, 965 and 863 cm^{-1} .

Preparation of machigline acetate: Machigline (6 mg) was treated with pyridine (3 drops) and Ac_2O (1 ml) and warmed for 10 min on water bath and then kept for 48 hr. After usual work-up, machigline acetate was obtained as red needles, m.p. 230°d from CHCl_3 -petrol mixture. ν_{max} 1730, 1640, 1575, 1522, 1460, 1250 and 962 cm^{-1} .

Conversion of machigline to dicentrinone: A methanolic solution (3 ml) of machigline (5 mg) was added to an excess of ethereal diazomethane solution when a yellow solid settled down due to its insolubility in ether. It was then kept with excess of the reagent at r.t. for 3 days. The yellow solid obtained after removal of ether was found to be a mixture of dicentrinone (identified by comparison of spectra of authentic dicentrinone obtained from Prof. M. P. Cava) and unreacted machigline, which was separated by chromatography. Dicentrinone (M^+ 335) had m.p. 300°d , crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH solution, ν_{max} 1640, 1052 and 962 cm^{-1} .

Isolation of 10-hydroxypalmitone from CHCl_3 extract: Separation of lignan constituents of *M. glaucescens* has been described in an earlier communication. Analysis of its aliphatic constituents resulted in the isolation of 10-hydroxypalmitone from CHCl_3 and CHCl_3 -MeOH (98 : 2) eluates of the main chromatogram, crystallised from pet. ether and CHCl_3 mixture as globules and from CHCl_3 -MeOH mixture as flakes, m.p. 96° , $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$ (CHCl_3), ν_{max} 3320, 2930, 2870 and 1706 cm^{-1} ; acetate, m.p. 43° (pet. ether-benzene), ν_{max} 1720 and 1240 cm^{-1} .

NaBH_4 reduction of 10-hydroxypalmitone to n-hentriacontan-10,16-diol: 10-Hydroxypalmitone (15 mg) was added to an excess of NaBH_4 in MeOH solution and was kept at r.t. for 40 hr. The diol (VII), m.p. 99° , was isolated after usual work-up and crystallisation from CHCl_3 -MeOH mixture, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$ (CHCl_3), ν_{max} 3300 cm^{-1} , m/e

(%) 450 (M^+ - H_2O , 4.5), 43 (m/e 450- H_2O , 11.2), 323 (20.9), 309 (32.2), 305 (13.9), 291 (19.1), 257 (8.8), 241 (40.6), 239 (83.5), 221 (47.5), 210 (17.7), 208 (13.6), 194 (8.8), 171 (21.8), 157 (15.5), 137 (20.7), 125 (23.7), 111 (39.9), 83 (100.0) and 57 (83.5).

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